

AI generated images for bad mathematics teaching in 2025

Jiří Šperka

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17483868>

Abstract

Articles When not use AI generated images in physics teaching¹ and AI generated images for bad physics teaching in 2025² deal with the use of generative artificial intelligence (AI) images for physics teaching. The aim of this article is to show, similarly, whether AI generated images should be used as tool for mathematics teaching in 2025. In my opinion no, AI generated images shouldn't be used for mathematics teaching.

AI generated example mathematics images

Presented pictures were generated using the free version of ChatGPT on October 28th, 2025. There is one generated image for each prompt because ChatGPT generated only one image as the answer to one single prompt.

First prompt input for ChatGPT was: *Show image that explains a quadratic function.* The generated result is in Fig. 1. There are more things that are not satisfactory in generated image. Numbers are missing on graph axes of quadratic function, axes are not labeled and letter h appears twice close to the point origin.

Second prompt input was: *Show image that explains Pythagorean theorem.* Response to this second prompt is in Fig. 2. The size of visualized squares doesn't correspond to the generated triangle in good way that would correspond to the Pythagorean theorem. Moreover, position of squares is not logical.

Third prompt input was: *Show image that explains prime numbers.* We can see generated result in Fig. 3. There are first six prime numbers in generated picture. The meaning of big circle with number 2 and arrow is not clear.

Conclusion

In 2025, AI generated pictures are not good for teaching of mathematics.

References

1. Šperka, J. (2024). When not use AI generated images in physics teaching. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14197274>
2. Šperka, J. (2025). AI generated images for bad physics teaching in 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17462798>

QUADRATIC FUNCTION

$$y = ax^2 + bx + c$$

Figure 1: AI generated image for first prompt.

PYTHAGOREAN THEOREM

$$a^2 + b^2 = c^2$$

Figure 2: AI generated image for second prompt.

PRIME NUMBERS

2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 13

ONLY TWO FACTORS

Figure 3: AI generated image for third prompt.